

Features

The frame and surface are not attached and therefore the surface can be positioned differently relative to the tip. There is enough space within the frame to align the tip along a groove of the surface, or against the peaks of the surface, and anywhere in between.

The tip can be rotated and locked using the stoppers. The blue cog has 12 teeth and the stoppers with the grey tip, lock the teeth parallel with the slider bar. The stoppers with the orange tips lock the cog between teeth. This allows 24 different angles to be explored (not accounting for rotational symmetry); this is equivalent to every 15° .

The slider's arm is not vertically fixed in position, allowing the tip to rise up and down in contact with the surface. This should also allow for a constant normal force.

Tweaks

If you wish to tweak the model, simply download and install BrickLink.com's free design program [Studio](#). Then you can use this program to open the design file for this model: "MiniCommensurabilityDemonstrator.io".

Parts list

To order this model please see “OrderingLEGO.pdf”.

List as .csv file: “MiniCommensurabilityDemonstrator.csv”.

Image	Description	Item No (& alternate Item Nos)	Colour	Qty
	Technic, Axle 32L	50450 13927	Black	2
	Plate, Modified 3 x 3 Cross	15397	Black	2
	Plate, Round 2 x 2 with Rounded Bottom	2654 54196 93791 28558	Bright Blue or Blue	48
	Technic, Gear 12 Tooth	69778	Bright Blue or Blue	1
	Technic, Brick 1 x 1 with Axle Hole	73230	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	8
	Technic, Brick 1 x 1 with Hole	6541	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	6
	Technic, Brick 1 x 2 with Axle Hole	32064 31493 32064b	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	8
	Brick 1 x 3	3622 3622f1 45505	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	32
	Brick 1 x 10	6111	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Brick 1 x 12	6112	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Brick 1 x 16	2465	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Plate 1 x 1	3024 28554 30008 63326	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	16
	Plate 1 x 3	3623	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	6
	Plate 1 x 4	3710	Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	4

	Plate, Modified 1 x 4 with 2 Studs without Groove	92593			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	1
	Plate 1 x 5	78329			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Plate 1 x 8	3460			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	22
	Plate 1 x 10	4477			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	2
	Plate 1 x 12	60479			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	10
	Wedge, Plate 3 x 3 Cut Corner	2450			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	20
	Tile, Round 2 x 2 with Open Stud	18674			Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	55
	Technic, Axle 5.5L with Stop	32209	59426		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	1
	Technic, Liftarm Thick 1 x 11	32525	64290		Dark Stone Grey or Dark Bluish Gray	1
	Technic, Axle 3L with Stud	6587	13670		Sand Yellow Dark Tan	2
	Technic, Arm with Gear 8 Tooth and 1.5L Axle	24014			Medium Stone Grey or Light Bluish Gray	2
	Technic, Plate Rotor 3 Blade with Smooth Ends and 6 Studs (Propeller)	32125	51138		Medium Stone Grey or Light Gray	2
	Technic Bush	3713	6590	42798	Medium Stone Grey or Light Gray	1
	Plate, Round 2 x 2 with Rounded Bottom	2654 28558	54196	93791	Bright Orange or Orange	7
	Tile 2 x 2	3068 3068b 1136	63327 78814	88409 113493	Bright Orange or Orange	4
	Slope 45 1 x 1 x 2/3 Double	35464			Bright Orange or Orange	2